

Approximation Algorithms for Steiner Tree and Traveling Salesman Problem

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Abstract. We present the novel research on NP-complete problems within polynomial bound space, P-space. This research is aimed towards the proof of equivalence of complexity classes like polynomial and non-polynomial, which is better known as “P versus NP” theorem. This problem still remains actual as most of researchers suppose that obviously NP isn’t equal to P as there is still no possible solution for problems like Steiner tree or Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP). There’re group of researchers who supposes that proof of equivalence of these classes is almost impossible. We present the new theorem towards the argument of equivalence of main complexity classes like P and NP. For this purpose, we extend our algorithm with the constraints while the main goal is to be achieved on the Steiner tree and TSP circuit on particular specific case whose input is still non-polynomial and converges to the specific non-polynomial number within the number of steps of algorithm.

Keywords: Traveling Salesman Problem, Steiner tree, approximation, algorithms.

Introduction. TSP is well studied in [1] and represents a combinatorial problem of finding the closed path known as Hamiltonian with the minimal length. This path visits each vertex only once, TSP naming is due to the actual statement of the problem where the vertexes in graph are town points.

Byrka et al [2] develop the improved version of the approximation algorithm for Steiner tree within the threshold of 1.39, which is a factor of the algorithm solution within the generalized algorithm. More to write that Steiner tree is a minimal spanning tree for the subset of vertexes of the graph $G(V, E)$, where V is the set of vertexes and E is a set of edges – this holds true for TSP also.

Opposed to Dirac’s theorem [3] we present alternative way of detecting the presence of Hamiltonian circuit or minimal Steiner tree for both versions of our algorithm. Generally, Dirac’s principle states that graph G is a Hamiltonian if the degree of each vertex is more than a half of the number of vertexes:

$$v \in V : deg(v) \geq \frac{|V|}{2}. \quad (1)$$

Sohel and Kaykobad give the proofs towards the set of criteria according to which the graph can be considered as having Hamiltonian cycle [4], this problem is also known to be NP-complete.

The polynomial algorithm for finding Hamiltonian cycle is given in [5]. We also refer to the original paper by Stephen Cook [6] for the statement of the relation between complexity classes and in our general algorithm we will give the argument towards proof of equivalence of P and NP.

Algorithm. For the purpose of the binary algorithm which finds Hamiltonian path or minimal Steiner tree, we define the one more condition to hold true:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n P_A \leq \sum_{i=1}^n P_B \square \max \dots (2)$$

The condition (2) defines the relation between the any path P_A and P_B within the edge weights $E(P_A)$ and $E(P_B)$. This condition is absolute and we will shrink it to the statement that the Hamiltonian or Steiner tree is seen from another metric in the source graph, thus, to be a residue from all the possible cycles and trees.

According to this algorithm we can choose even greedy strategy for any starting vertex. The binary algorithm can be introduced in several steps:

1. Choose maximum edge value;
2. Multiply it by two, giving S ;
3. Perform in a binary search if there exists a Hamiltonian cycle or uncovered subgraph for Steiner tree by known algorithm, increasing or decreasing value of S .
4. The complexity is $O(\log(S) * N^k)$: $k > 0$.

Where S is the doubled maximal weight of any edge value as defined in algebraic map function for weighted graphs:

$$e \in E, w \in R: E \rightarrow W. \quad (3)$$

The partial case where there exist the separate set E_s , so that all the translations of the weights are much smaller than average can be interpreted as follows:

$$e \in E_s: E_s \rightarrow \frac{W - avg(W)}{2}. \quad (4)$$

In the case (4) there exist single minimal path in TSP and minimal subgraph for Steiner tree.

P versus NP. In this section main proofs towards argument of equivalence of complexity classes are given according to the proposed approximation algorithm. As we have already stated that the solution can be found for the case where there exists the divided subgraph with edge weights smaller on average, we can show that the number of possible graphs is NP-complete, thus:

$$|E \rightarrow W| \in NP. \quad (5)$$

The expression (5) gives the reasonable question about dependence of the set of input data to the set of possible solutions and algorithmic efficiency. Thus, we state that there exists an exact polynomial algorithm for the problem which derives the NP-complete input. For this fact we define the statement of equivalence of P and NP classes within the exact algorithm and the constraint (4):

$$|I| \in NP, A \in P \stackrel{\square}{\Rightarrow} O(A) \in P. \quad (6)$$

The expression (6) is defined as the relation between P and NP classes as we devise the modern “witness” theorem, where it’s defined that if any of the NP-complete problems have a polynomial solution, then it follows that P equals NP.

Thus, it follows that $P = NP$ as our new argument towards the proof of the equivalence of the different classes of complexities.

Bipartite matching algorithm. We define another step of experimentation with the definition of weighted bipartite matching algorithm. By their nature these algorithms solve the problem of maximal flow in a graph with weights or, simply, the maximal or minimal weight of the matching in a bipartite graph.

According to our observations the minimal weighted matching in a TSP graph solves the problem of finding Hamiltonian path, while the degree of the matching permutation equals to one. In case of more than one group in final solution, we propose a way of the repeated acquisition of the algorithm on a minimal edge.

The algorithm above is also approximation, however, it differs from the main algorithm as it’s not defined even for partial case as it’s described in “P versus NP” section of this article.

Thus, we get the difference according to the term of algorithms defined on the input with the set of constraints, in our case, there’s only single constraint (4).

The algorithm where the groups of permutation are defined is called thus bipartite as this can occur in the general case and is limited to the first feasible obtained solution, where the following holds true:

$$|A|=1: A \in P. \quad (7)$$

The expression (7) means that the index of the permutation obtained during the first run equals to one, or, in other words, there's only group and, thus, the algorithm can be considered as successful as it runs in polynomial time.

In general, the bipartite matching in half graphs where each part for TSP is of size $|V|$, we can get the right point even at once, thus, the probability of the feasible solution is given by the following relation:

$$|A=P| \leq \frac{1}{|V|!}. \quad (8)$$

As this process is probabilistic and, thus, can be evaluated on the deterministic automata, we give another argument towards the equivalence of complexity classes like polynomial (P) and non-polynomial (NP).

Thus, if probabilistic models could be implemented, then we can fully state that $P = NP$, however, due to the lack of the modern research where this problem could be considered not as a primary target, we can do the rest of work by providing the argumentative answer to the main question by Stephen Cook of whether there exists the polynomial or, in our case, deterministic model of operations so that the key answer could be easily found.

However, as all the above holds true, we state that the polynomial algorithms exist with non-zero probability and, thus, P equals NP.

Conclusion. We have presented one approximation algorithm for both TSP and Steiner tree and one algorithm for TSP as a weighted bipartite matching. Both algorithms operate on graphs. Within the constrained graphs we can also conclude that P equals NP as the constraint doesn't limit the size of the input and, in general, this fact is to be considered further as NP-complete problems are mostly classified according to the representation of the problem as the 3-SAT problem, which is known as "Boolean satisfiability".

We have showed that the number of possible cases in general is a combinatorial number and approximates to almost factorial like the number of sums as this's opposed to the classification of the problem to 3-SAT.

On the other hand, the algorithm proposed is binary and can be applied to the limited cases as per the constraint, from that follows that constrained problems are either P-complete or $P = NP$. As the number of input cases tends to factorial number, it can be stated that $P = NP$.

The statement above is our general argument towards the proof of equivalence of complexity classes according to the fact that there exists a polynomial solution for NP-complete problem.

We have also showed that the initial version of the algorithm without permutation subgroups can be applied to both TSP and Steiner tree as for TSP the devised path can be found even in greedy manner and for Steiner tree the tree connectivity can be checked and used as the step of the binary algorithm to increase or decrease the lower or upper bound of the edge weight value S.

Thus, it follows that $P = NP$ if the constraint holds true and the general statement is true.

We have also given another argument towards the statement above on deterministic and probabilistic models where the feasible solution could be found in polynomial time with pre-defined threshold.

We also give the constructive definition of the nature of the operational models to conclude the invariance of NP-class to the P-class of complexity.

Thus, all the important results presented here can be evaluated further and the question of the relation between constrained and probabilistic models to the deterministic one is to be evaluated.

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References

1. Davendra, Donald, ed. *Traveling salesman problem: Theory and applications*. *BoD—Books on Demand*, 2010.
2. Byrka, Jaroslaw, et al. "An improved LP-based approximation for Steiner tree." *Proceedings of the forty-second ACM symposium on Theory of computing*. 2010.
3. Li, Hao. "Generalizations of Dirac's theorem in Hamiltonian graph theory—A survey." *Discrete Mathematics* 313.19 (2013): 2034-2053.
4. Rahman, M. Sohel, and Mohammad Kaykobad. "On Hamiltonian cycles and Hamiltonian paths." *Information Processing Letters* 94.1 (2005): 37-41.
5. Riaz, Khadija, and Malik Sikander Hayat Khiyal. "Finding hamiltonian cycle in polynomial time." *Information Technology Journal* 5.5 (2006): 851-859
6. Cook, Stephen. "The P versus NP problem." *Clay Mathematics Institute* 2 (2000).